

Table e-1: MRI acquisition parameters

Sequence	Feature	Sporadic SVD (RUN DMC – inTENse study)	CADASIL (VASCAMY study)	
	Scanner	Magnetom Prisma	Magnetom Skyra	Magnetom Prisma
	Coil channels	32 (head)	64 (head-neck)	64 (head-neck)
3D-T1	Type	MP2RAGE	MPRAGE	-
	TR [ms]	5500	2500	-
	TE [ms]	3.84	4.37	-
	TI [ms]	700/2500 ^a	1100	-
	Flip angle [°]	7/4 ^a	7	-
	Voxel size [mm]	0.85 isotropic	1 isotropic	-
3D-FLAIR	TR [ms]	5000	5000	-
	TE [ms]	394	398	-
	TI [ms]	1800	1800	-
	Voxel size [mm]	0.85 isotropic	1 isotropic	-
3D-GRE	TR [ms]	35	35	-
	TE [ms]	29.5	29.5	-
	Flip angle [°]	15	15	-
	Voxel size [mm]	0.8 x 0.8 x 2	0.9 x 0.9 x 2	-
MS-DWI	TR [ms]	3220	3800	3200
	TE [ms]	74	104.8	74
	Flip angle [°]	90	90	90
	In-plane resolution [mm]	1.7 x 1.7	2 x 2	2 x 2
	Slice thickness [mm]	1.7	2	2
	Base resolution (matrix)	130	120	120
	Number of slices	87	75	75
	b-values [s/mm ²]	1000/3000	1000/2000	1000/2000
	Directions (per b-value)	30/60	30/60	30/60
	b=0 [images]	10	10	10
	Receiver bandwidth [Hz/px]	1924	1894	1954
	Parallel imaging acceleration factor	2	2	2
	Multi-band acceleration factor	3	3	3

^a Double inversion

Abbreviations: CADASIL = Cerebral Autosomal Dominant Arteriopathy with Subcortical Infarcts and Leukoencephalopathy; FLAIR = fluid-attenuated inversion recovery; GRE = gradient echo; MP(2)RAGE = magnetization prepared (2) rapid acquisition gradient echo(es); MS-DWI = multi shell diffusion-weighted imaging; SVD = small vessel disease; TE = echo time; TI = inversion time; TR = repetition time.